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Abstract:

In this paper, we offer a new class of sets called $(1, 2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets in bitopological spaces and we study some of its basic properties. It turns out that this class lies between the class of $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed sets and the class of $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed sets.

Key Words: bitopological space, $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed set, $(1, 2)^*$ - g''' -closed set, $(1, 2)^*$ - g''' -open set & $(1, 2)^*$ - ω -closed set

1. Introduction:

In 1963 Levine [19] introduced the notion of semi-open sets. According to Cameron [7] this notion was Levine's most important contribution to the field of topology. The motivation behind the introduction of semi-open sets was a problem of Kelley which Levine has considered in [20], i.e., to show that $\text{cl}(U) = \text{cl}(U \cap D)$ for all open sets U and dense sets D . He proved that U is semi-open if and only if $\text{cl}(U) = \text{cl}(U \cap D)$ for all dense sets D and D is dense if and only if $\text{cl}(U) = \text{cl}(U \cap D)$ for all semi-open sets U . Since the advent of the notion of semi-open sets, many mathematicians worked on such sets and also introduced some other notions, among others, preopen sets [22], α -open sets [25] and β -open sets [1] (Andrijevic [3] called them semi-pre open sets). It has been shown in [11] recently that the notion of preopen sets and semi-open sets are important with respect to the digital plane.

Levine [18] also introduced the notion of g -closed sets and investigated its fundamental properties. This notion was shown to be productive and very useful. For example it is shown that g -closed sets can be used to characterize the extremally disconnected spaces and the submaximal spaces (see [8] and [9]). Moreover the study of g -closed sets led to some separation axioms between T_0 and T_1 which proved to be useful in computer science and digital topology (see [17] and [14]).

Recently, Bhattacharya and Lahiri [5], Arya and Nour [4], Sheik John [31] and Rajamani and Viswanathan [28] introduced sg -closed sets, gs -closed sets, ω -closed sets and αgs -closed sets respectively.

In this paper, we introduce a new class of sets namely $(1, 2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets in bitopological spaces. This class lies between the class of closed sets and the class of $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed sets. This class also lies between the class of closed sets and the class of $(1, 2)^*$ - ω -closed sets.

2. Preliminaries:

Throughout this paper (X, τ) and (Y, σ) (or X and Y) represent topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless otherwise mentioned. For a subset A of a space (X, τ) , $\text{cl}(A)$, $\text{int}(A)$ and A^c denote the closure of A , the interior of A and the complement of A respectively. We recall the following definitions which are useful in the sequel.

Definition 2.1:

A subset A of a space (X, τ) is called:

- (i) $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open set [19] if $A \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))$;
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ -preopen set [22] if $A \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$;
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open set [25] if $A \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)))$;
- (iv) $(1, 2)^*$ - β -open set [1] (= $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-preopen [3]) if $A \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)))$;
- (v) regular $(1, 2)^*$ -open set [32] if $A = \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$.

The complements of the above mentioned $\tau_{1,2}$ -open sets are called their respective $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed sets.

The $(1, 2)^*$ -preclosure [26] (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closure [10], $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closure [25], $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-pre-closure [3]) of a subset A of X , denoted by $(1, 2)^*\text{-pcl}(A)$ (resp. $(1, 2)^*\text{-scl}(A)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{-cl}(A)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-spcl}(A)$) is defined to be the intersection of all $(1, 2)^*$ -preclosed (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-preclosed) sets of X containing A . It is known that $(1, 2)^*\text{-pcl}(A)$ (resp. $(1, 2)^*\text{-scl}(A)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{-cl}(A)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-spcl}(A)$) is a $(1, 2)^*$ -preclosed (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-closed, $(1, 2)^*$ - α -closed, $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-preclosed) set. For any subset A of an arbitrarily chosen bitopological space, the $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-interior [10] (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α -interior [25], $(1, 2)^*$ -preinterior [26]) of A , denoted by $(1, 2)^*\text{-sint}(A)$ (resp. $(1, 2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{-int}(A)$, $(1, 2)^*\text{-pint}(A)$), is defined to be the union of all $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open (resp. $(1, 2)^*$ - α -open, $(1, 2)^*$ -preopen) sets of X contained in A .

Definition 2.2:

A subset A of a bitopological space X is called

- (i) $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized closed (briefly, $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed) set [18] if $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\tau_{1,2}$ -open in X .
The complement of $(1, 2)^*$ - g -closed set is called $(1, 2)^*$ - g -open set;
- (ii) $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-generalized closed (briefly, $(1, 2)^*$ - sg -closed) set [5] if $(1, 2)^*\text{-scl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(1, 2)^*$ -semi-open in X .
The complement of sg -closed set is called sg -open set;
- (iii) $(1, 2)^*$ -generalized semi-closed (briefly, $(1, 2)^*$ - gs -closed) set [4] if $(1, 2)^*\text{-scl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\tau_{1,2}$ -open in X .

- The complement of $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed set is called $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set;
- (iv) $(1,2)^*$ - α -generalized closed (briefly, $(1,2)^*$ - α g-closed) set [21] if $(1,2)^*$ - α cl(A) \subseteq U whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\tau_{1,2}$ -open in X.
The complement of $(1,2)^*$ - α g-closed set is called $(1,2)^*$ - α g-open set;
- (v) $(1,2)^*$ -generalized semi-preclosed (briefly, $(1,2)^*$ -gsp-closed) set [26] if $(1,2)^*$ -spcl(A) \subseteq U whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\tau_{1,2}$ -open in X.
The complement of $(1,2)^*$ -gsp-closed set is called $(1,2)^*$ -gsp-open set;
- (vi) $(1,2)^*$ - \hat{g} -closed set [33] ($(1,2)^*$ - ω -closed [31]) if $\tau_{1,2}$ -cl(A) \subseteq U whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open in X.
The complement of $(1,2)^*$ - \hat{g} -closed set is called $(1,2)^*$ - \hat{g} -open set;
- (vii) $(1,2)^*$ - α gs-closed set [28] if $(1,2)^*$ - α cl(A) \subseteq U whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open in X.
The complement of $(1,2)^*$ - α gs-closed set is called $(1,2)^*$ - α gs-open set;
- (viii) $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-closed set [23] if $(1,2)^*$ -scl(A) \subseteq U whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open in X.
The complement of $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-closed set is called $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-open set;
- (ix) $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed set [29] if $(1,2)^*$ - α cl(A) \subseteq U whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open in X.
The complement of $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed set is called $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -open set.

Remark 2.3:

The collection of all $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed (resp. $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed, $(1,2)^*$ - ω -closed, $(1,2)^*$ -g-closed, $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed, $(1,2)^*$ -gsp-closed, $(1,2)^*$ - α g-closed, $(1,2)^*$ - α gs-closed, $(1,2)^*$ -sg-closed, $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-closed, $(1,2)^*$ - α -closed, $(1,2)^*$ -semi-closed) sets is denoted by $(1,2)^*$ - G'''' C(X) (resp. $(1,2)^*$ - G'''' C(X), $(1,2)^*$ - ω C(X), $(1,2)^*$ -G C(X), $(1,2)^*$ -GS C(X), $(1,2)^*$ -GSP C(X), $(1,2)^*$ - α g C(X), $(1,2)^*$ - α GS C(X), $(1,2)^*$ -SG C(X), $(1,2)^*$ -G*SC(X), $(1,2)^*$ - α C(X), $(1,2)^*$ -S C(X)).

The collection of all $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -open (resp. $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -open, $(1,2)^*$ - ω -open, $(1,2)^*$ -g-open, $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open, $(1,2)^*$ -gsp-open, $(1,2)^*$ - α g-open, $(1,2)^*$ - α gs-open, $(1,2)^*$ -sg-open, $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-open, $(1,2)^*$ - α -open, $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open) sets is denoted by $(1,2)^*$ - G'''' O(X) (resp. $(1,2)^*$ - G'''' O(X), $(1,2)^*$ - ω O(X), $(1,2)^*$ -G O(X), $(1,2)^*$ -GS O(X), $(1,2)^*$ -GSP O(X), $(1,2)^*$ - α g O(X), $(1,2)^*$ - α GS O(X), $(1,2)^*$ -SG O(X), $(1,2)^*$ -G*SO(X), $(1,2)^*$ - α O(X), $(1,2)^*$ -S O(X)).

We denote the power set of X by P(X).

Definition 2.4 [16]:

A subset S of X is said to be $(1,2)^*$ -locally closed if $S = U \cap F$, where U is $\tau_{1,2}$ -open and F is $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed in X.

Result 2.5:

- (1) Every $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set is $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-open [23].
- (2) Every $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open set is $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-open [23].
- (3) Every $(1,2)^*$ -g*s-open set is $(1,2)^*$ -sg-open [23].
- (4) Every $(1,2)^*$ -semi-closed set is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed [24].
- (5) Every $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed [12].

Corollary 2.6 [27]:

Let A be both $\tau_{1,2}$ -open and $(1,2)^*$ -sg-closed set and suppose that F is $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set. Then $A \cap F$ is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed set.

3. $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -Closed Sets:

We introduce the following definition.

Definition 3.1:

A subset A of X is called a $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed set if $\tau_{1,2}$ -cl(A) \subseteq U whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open in X.

Proposition 3.2:

Every $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed.

Proof:

If A is any $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set in X and G is any $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set containing A, then $G \supseteq A = \tau_{1,2}$ -cl(A). Hence A is $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed. The converse of Proposition 3.2 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.3:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then G'''' C(X) = $\{\emptyset, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{a, c\}$ is g'''' -closed set but not closed.

Proposition 3.4:

Every $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed set is $(1,2)^*$ - g'''' -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed subset of X and G is any $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set containing A , then $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \supseteq (1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{cl}(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''_{\alpha}$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.4 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.5:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\emptyset, \{a, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''_{\alpha}C(X) = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{a\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''_{\alpha}$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.6:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g^*\text{s}$ -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed subset of X and G is any $(1,2)^*\text{-}gs$ -open set containing A , then $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \supseteq (1,2)^*\text{-scl}(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g^*\text{s}$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.6 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.7:

In Example 3.5, $(1,2)^*\text{-}G^*\text{SC}(X) = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g^*\text{s}$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.8:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega$ -closed.

Proof:

Suppose that $A \subseteq G$ and G is $(1,2)^*\text{-semi}$ -open in X . Since every $(1,2)^*\text{-semi}$ -open set is $(1,2)^*\text{-gs}$ -open and A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed, therefore $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq G$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.8 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.9:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega C(X) = P(X)$. Here, $A = \{a, c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.10:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g^*\text{s}$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-sg}$ -closed.

Proof:

Suppose that $A \subseteq G$ and G is $(1,2)^*\text{-semi}$ -open in X . Since every $(1,2)^*\text{-semi}$ -open set is $(1,2)^*\text{-gs}$ -open and A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g^*\text{s}$ -closed, therefore $(1,2)^*\text{-scl}(A) \subseteq G$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-sg}$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.10 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.11:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G^*\text{SC}(X) = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-SGC}(X) = P(X)$. Here, $A = \{a, b\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-sg}$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g^*\text{s}$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.12:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g s$ -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega$ -closed subset of X and G is any $(1,2)^*\text{-semi}$ -open set containing A , then $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \supseteq (1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{cl}(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g s$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.12 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.13:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega C(X) = \{\emptyset, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha G S C(X) = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{b\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g s$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}\omega$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.14:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-g}$ -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed subset of X and G is any open set containing A , since every $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set is $(1,2)^*\text{-gs}$ -open, we have $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-g}$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.14 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.15:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}G C(X) = P(X)$. Here, $A = \{a, b\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-g}$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.16:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g s$ -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed subset of X and G is any $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open set containing A , since every $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open set is $(1,2)^*$ - gs -open, we have $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \supseteq (1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{cl}(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha gs$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.16 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.17:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha GS C(X) = P(X)$. Here, $A = \{a, c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha gs$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.18:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g$ -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed subset of X and G is any $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set containing A , since every $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gs$ -open, we have $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \supseteq (1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha\text{cl}(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.18 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.19:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g C(X) = P(X)$. Here, $A = \{a, c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha g$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.20:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gs$ -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed subset of X and G is any $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set containing A , since every $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gs$ -open, we have $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \supseteq (1,2)^*\text{-}scl(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gs$ -closed in X . The converse of Proposition 3.20 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.21:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\phi, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}GS C(X) = \{\phi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gs$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Proposition 3.22:

Every $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gsp$ -closed.

Proof:

If A is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed subset of X and G is any $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set containing A , every $\tau_{1,2}$ -open set is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gs$ -open, we have $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \supseteq (1,2)^*\text{-}spcl(A)$. Hence A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gsp$ -closed in X .

The converse of Proposition 3.22 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.23:

In Example 3.21, $(1,2)^*\text{-}GSP C(X) = \{\phi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}gsp$ -closed but not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set in X .

Remark 3.24:

The following example shows that $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed sets are independent of $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -closed sets and $(1,2)^*\text{-}semi$ -closed sets.

Example 3.25:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\phi, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha C(X) = S C(X) = \{\phi, \{c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{a, c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed but it is neither $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -closed nor $(1,2)^*\text{-}semi$ -closed in X .

Example 3.26:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\phi, \{b, c\}, X\}$ and $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha C(X) = S C(X) = \{\phi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Here, $A = \{b\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}\alpha$ -closed as well as $(1,2)^*\text{-}semi$ -closed in X but it is not $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed in X .

Remark 3.27:

From the above discussions and known results in [28, 31, 33], we obtain the following diagram, where $A \rightarrow B$ (resp. $A \leftarrow B$) represents A implies B but not conversely (resp. A and B are independent of each other).

None of the above implications is reversible as shown in the remaining examples and in the related papers [28, 31, 33].

4. Properties of $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -Closed Sets:

In this section, we have proved that an arbitrary intersection of $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed. Moreover, we discuss some basic properties of $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets.

Definition 4.1:

The intersection of all $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open subsets of X containing A is called the $(1,2)^*$ -gs-kernel of A and denoted by $(1,2)^*$ -gs-ker(A).

Lemma 4.2:

A subset A of X is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed if and only if $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$.

Proof:

Suppose that A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed. Then $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open. Let $x \in \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$. If $x \notin (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$, then there is a $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set U containing A such that $x \notin U$. Since U is a $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set containing A , we have $x \notin \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$ and this is a contradiction.

Conversely, let $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$. If U is any $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set containing A , then $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A) \subseteq U$. Therefore, A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

Proposition 4.3:

For any subset A of X , $X_2 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$, where $X_2 = \{x \in X : \{x\} \text{ is } (1,2)^*\text{-preopen}\}$.

Proof:

Let $x \in X_2 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$ and suppose that $x \notin (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$. Then there is a $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set U containing A such that $x \notin U$. If $F = X - U$, then F is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed. Since $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\{x\}) \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$, we have $\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\{x\})) \subseteq A \cup \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$. Again since $x \in X_2$, we have $x \notin X_1$ and so $\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\{x\})) = \emptyset$. Therefore, there has to be some $y \in A \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\{x\}))$ and hence $y \in F \cap A$, a contradiction.

Theorem 4.4:

A subset A of X is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed if and only if $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq A$, where $X_1 = \{x \in X : \{x\} \text{ is } (1,2)^*\text{-nowhere dense}\}$.

Proof:

Suppose that A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed. Let $x \in X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$. Then $x \in X_1$ and $x \in \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$. Since $x \in X_1$, $\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\{x\})) = \emptyset$. Therefore, $\{x\}$ is $(1,2)^*$ -semi-closed, since $\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\{x\})) \subseteq \{x\}$. Since every $(1,2)^*$ -semi-closed set is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed [Result 2.5 (4)], $\{x\}$ is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-closed. If $x \notin A$ and if $U = X \setminus \{x\}$, then U is a $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open set containing A and so $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq U$, a contradiction.

Conversely, suppose that $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq A$. Then $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$, since $A \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$. Now $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) = X \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) = (X_1 \cup X_2) \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) = (X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)) \cup (X_2 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)) \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$, since $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq (1,2)^*\text{-gs-ker}(A)$ and Proposition 4.3. Thus, A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed by Lemma 4.2.

Theorem 4.5:

An arbitrary intersection of $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

Proof:

Let $F = \{A_i : i \in \wedge\}$ be a family of $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets and let $A = \bigcap_{i \in \wedge} A_i$. Since $A \subseteq A_i$ for each i , $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A_i)$ for each i . Using Theorem 4.4 for each $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set A_i , we have $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A_i) \subseteq A_i$. Thus, $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A_i) \subseteq A_i$ for each $i \in \wedge$. That is, $X_1 \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq A$ and so A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed by Theorem 4.4.

Corollary 4.6:

If A is a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set and F is a $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set, then $A \cap F$ is a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set.

Proof:

Since F is closed, it is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed. Therefore by Theorem 4.5, $A \cap F$ is also a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set.

Proposition 4.7:

If A and B are $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets in X , then $A \cup B$ is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X .

Proof:

If $A \cup B \subseteq G$ and G is $(1,2)^*$ -gs-open, then $A \subseteq G$ and $B \subseteq G$. Since A and B are $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed, $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$ and $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(B)$ and hence $G \supseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \cup \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(B) = \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A \cup B)$. Thus $A \cup B$ is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set in X .

Proposition 4.8:

If a set A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X , then $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$ contains no nonempty $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set in X .

Proof:

Suppose that A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed. Let F be a $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed subset of $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Then $A \subseteq F^c$. But A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed, therefore $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq F^c$. Consequently, $F \subseteq (\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))^c$. We already have $F \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$. Thus $F \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \cap (\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))^c$ and F is empty.

The converse of Proposition 4.8 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 4.9:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*G(X) = \{\emptyset, \{b, c\}, X\}$. If $A = \{b\}$, then $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A = \{c\}$ does not contain any nonempty $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set. But A is not $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X .

Theorem 4.10:

A set A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed if and only if $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$ contains no nonempty $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set.

Proof:

Necessity. Suppose that A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed. Let S be a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed subset of $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Then $A \subseteq S^c$. Since A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed, we have $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq S^c$. Consequently, $S \subseteq (\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))^c$. Hence, $S \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \cap (\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))^c = \emptyset$. Therefore S is empty.

Sufficiency. Suppose that $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$ contains no nonempty $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set. Let $A \subseteq G$ and G be both $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed and $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -open. If $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \not\subseteq G$, then $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \cap G^c \neq \emptyset$. Since $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$ is a $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set and G^c is both $\tau_{1,2}$ -open and $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set, $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \cap G^c$ is a nonempty $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed subset of $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$ (from Corollary 2.6). This is a contradiction. Therefore, $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq G$ and hence A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

Proposition 4.11:

If A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X and $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$, then B is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X .

Proof:

Since $B \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$, we have $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(B) \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$. Then, $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(B) - B \subseteq \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Since $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) - A$ has no nonempty $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed subsets, neither does $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(B) - B$. By Theorem 4.10, B is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

Proposition 4.12:

Let $A \subseteq Y \subseteq X$ and suppose that A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X . Then A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed relative to Y .

Proof:

Let $A \subseteq Y \cap G$, where G is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -open in X . Then $A \subseteq G$ and hence $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq G$. This implies that $Y \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq Y \cap G$. Thus A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed relative to Y .

Proposition 4.13:

If A is a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -open and $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X , then A is closed in X .

Proof:

Since A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -open and $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed, $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq A$ and hence A is $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed in X .

Recall that a bitopological space X is called $(1,2)^*$ -extremally disconnected if $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(U)$ is $\tau_{1,2}$ -open for each $U \in \tau_{1,2}$.

Theorem 4.14:

Let X be $(1,2)^*$ -extremally disconnected and A a $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open subset of X . Then A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed if and only if it is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

Proof:

It follows from the fact that if X is $(1,2)^*$ -extremally disconnected and A is a $(1,2)^*$ -semi-open subset of X , then $(1,2)^*\text{scl}(A) = \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)$ (Lemma 0.3 [15]).

Theorem 4.15:

Let A be a $(1,2)^*$ -locally closed set of X . Then A is $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed if and only if A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii). It is fact that every $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed set is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). By Proposition 5.1.3.3 of Bourbaki [6], $A \cup (X - \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$ is $\tau_{1,2}$ -open in X , since A is $(1,2)^*$ -locally closed. Now $A \cup (X - \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$ is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -open set of X such that $A \subseteq A \cup (X - \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$. Since A is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed, then $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq A \cup (X - \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$. Thus, we have $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq A$ and hence A is a $\tau_{1,2}$ -closed.

Proposition 4.16:

For each $x \in X$, either $\{x\}$ is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed or $\{x\}^c$ is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X .

Proof:

Suppose that $\{x\}$ is not $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X . Then $\{x\}^c$ is not $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -open and the only $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -open set containing $\{x\}^c$ is the space X itself. Therefore $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\{x\}^c) \subseteq X$ and so $\{x\}^c$ is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed in X .

Theorem 4.17:

Let A be a $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed set of a bitopological space X . Then,

- (i) $(1,2)^*$ -sint(A) is $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.
- (ii) If A is regular $(1,2)^*$ -open, then $(1,2)^*$ -pint(A) and $(1,2)^*$ -scl(A) are also $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed sets.
- (iii) If A is regular $(1,2)^*$ -closed, then $(1,2)^*$ -pcl(A) is also $(1,2)^*$ - g''' -closed.

Proof:

- (i) Since $\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))$ is a closed set in X, by Corollary 4.6, $(1,2)^*\text{-sint}(A) = A \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed in X.
- (ii) Since A is regular $(1,2)^*$ -open in X, $A = \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A))$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-scl}(A) = A \cup \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)) = A$. Thus, $(1,2)^*\text{-scl}(A)$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed in X. Since $(1,2)^*\text{-pint}(A) = A \cap \tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(A)) = A$, $(1,2)^*\text{-pint}(A)$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed.
- (iii) Since A is regular $(1,2)^*$ -closed in X, $A = \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(A))$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-pcl}(A) = A \cup \tau_{1,2}\text{-cl}(\tau_{1,2}\text{-int}(A)) = A$. Thus, $(1,2)^*\text{-pcl}(A)$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed in X.

The converses of the statements in the Theorem 4.17 are not true as we see in the following examples.

Example 4.18:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the set $A = \{b\}$ is not a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed set. However $(1,2)^*\text{-sint}(A) = \phi$ is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed.

Example 4.19:

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\tau = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then $(1,2)^*\text{-}G'''C(X) = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then the set $A = \{c\}$ is not regular $(1,2)^*$ -open. However A is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed and $(1,2)^*\text{-scl}(A) = \{c\}$ is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed and $(1,2)^*\text{-pint}(A) = \phi$ is also $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed.

Example 4.20:

In Example 4.19, the set $A = \{c\}$ is not regular $(1,2)^*$ -closed. However A is a $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed and $(1,2)^*\text{-pcl}(A) = \{c\}$ is $(1,2)^*\text{-}g'''$ -closed.

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